

RISK ANALYSIS AND SAFETY SYSTEMS EVALUATION OF A NEW ALPINE RAILWAY TUNNEL

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ABSTRACT

The risk analysis of a new ca. 13 kilometers long twin track railway tunnel in Northern Italy is presented herein. Two important criteria are thereby highlighted: the operability of the line defined in terms of expected shut down and the societal risk derived in terms of expected human losses. The influence of the safety measures is discussed and recommendations for future risk criteria are provided.

1. INTRODUCTION

The railway is moving now rapidly towards a modern service transportation industry. High-Speed Rail (HSR) systems are already operating in Japan, England, France, Italy and Germany. A further development of the whole European HSR network is planned. In order to guarantee the design velocities of approximately 250 km/h a considerable part of the routes is in tunnels. Many of the planned tunnels have lengths greater than 10 kilometers and in four cases reach values of the order of 50 kilometers. Although railway is generally considered as a safe transportation system (for example an order of magnitude safer than the transportation by road) the safety problem has been raised since accidental consequences in long tunnels can be significant. The safety of tunnels becomes therefore an important aspect for the design and operation of HSR systems.

The Italian State Railway is currently upgrading the existing line between Verona in Northern Italy, via the Brenner Pass into Austria; part of the plan is for a major new ca. 13 kilometers long twin track tunnel. This contribution reflects experience gained from the risk analysis of the aforementioned tunnel and recommends safety criteria for the long railway tunnels of the future European railway network.

In a first step all important hazard scenarios affecting the operability and the safety of the tunnel are identified and classified into different categories. For the significant hazard scenarios a probabilistic event-tree analysis is carried out in a second step by using accident statistics to evaluate occurrence probabilities of initiating and subsequent events.

In a third step the influence of safety measures is discussed and quantified on the basis of expert opinion. A development of the planned prevention and mitigation measures is evaluated by means of sensitivity analyses and cost considerations. The acceptability of the overall risk level of the upgraded line is discussed and recommendations for future safety criteria are provided.

2. IDENTIFICATION OF HAZARD SCENARIOS

The subject tunnel is part of the important North Italian Railway line Verona-Brennero characterized by a considerable amount of traffic, i.e. 270 trains per day in both directions; ca 45% of the traffic is associated to transportation of goods.

Accident statistics and safety in railway transportation have been discussed in the past (see for example Metz and Köller, 1988) and special problems such as the transportation of dangerous materials (Diamantidis et al., 1988) safety and operability of HSR systems (D'Appolonia, 1987) and risk in long tunnels (Bohnenblust & Schneider, 1984; Kampmann et al., 1989) have been also addressed. The first task in a safety study concerns the identification of the important hazard scenarios.

Generally, an accidental scenario is characterized by the following course:

- o primary cause;
- o initiating event;
- o accident pattern;
- o consequences.

The primary cause can be classified into:

- o internal causes (mechanical or electrical failures, concerning the control guide system as well as the logistic and in service systems);
- o external causes (earthquakes, floods, avalanches, snowslides);
- o causes associated to human action (e.g. operation faults, maintenance of short quality, sabotages, terroristic attacks).

Based on a critical review of Italian Railway accidents of the last two decades the following dominating initiating events have been identified:

- o derailment;
- o collision;
- o crash against obstacles;
- o fire;
- o stop of the train (only for the operability criteria).

The accident propagation and the consequences have been evaluated on the basis of a risk analysis approach.

As it is general practice in the performance analysis of an industrial system, two different criteria have been considered associated to:

- a) operability or availability of the railway line in the subject tunnel defined in terms of the expected shut down time of system;
- b) safety of the line inside the tunnel represented by the expected number of human losses.

3. RISK ANALYSIS APPROACH

The applied risk analysis approach consists of three basic steps, i.e.:

- o statistical evaluation of accidental rates;
- o modelization of the accidental scenarios (propagation of accidents) through event trees;
- o assessment of the consequences.

3.1 Statistical Evaluation of Accidental Rates

The quantitative analysis of the occurrence probabilities associated to the selected initiating events requires the knowledge of traffic volume data as well as the number of accidents of the subject line.

The statistical data, drawn by the Italian Railway reports of the last 20 years, have suitably been calibrated to take into account the increased safety level during the last years (in terms of material quality, protection devices, ect.) and the presence of the tunnel itself, i.e. those accidents that cannot happen inside the tunnels have been screened out.

Table 1 illustrates the computed occurrence rates for each initiating event.

The occurrence probabilities associated to each initiating event can be calculated by assuming events to follow a Poisson process. Thereby a frequentistic or a Bayesian approach can be implemented (Benjamin and Cornell, 1968). However since the amount of available accident data is sufficient a frequentistic approach has been applied.

3.2 Event Tree Approach

A quantitative risk analysis has been performed to determine the propagation of every accidental scenario associated to the two different criteria, i.e.:

- o availability of the line;
- o societal risk.

An event tree approach has been applied since it represents a straightforward procedure for describing the accidental scenarios and it can include different variables and notions of time. A deductive logic has been used to construct the event trees; that is, starting with an initiating event, possible sequences of following events are layed out and the outcome of each considered sequence is determined.

In order to construct the event trees, block diagrams have been first defined such as the one illustrated in Figure 1 and associated to the derailment event. The sequences of the derailment event have been then implemented in the binary logic of an event tree.

In order to simplify computations two different types of basic events have been classified, i.e. generic events, which are independent of the particular situation of traffic in the tunnel, and specific events, which depend on the traffic characteristics.

In the case of derailment the specified generic basic events are the following:

- o the other track is occupied;
- o mechanical damage;
- o fire;
- o explosion;
- o release of toxic gases;

while the specific basic events are:

- o trains in the opposite direction are stopped;
- o collision against a:
 - passenger train,
 - goods train (dangerous material not involved),
 - goods train (dangerous material involved).

For example, among the generic events, those defined as release of toxic gases, represent the scenario that toxic gases can be released given the occurrence of an accident in which dangerous material is involved. On the other hand the specific event defined as dangerous goods are present, reflects the fact that only a percentage of the transported goods is dangerous.

By means of this procedure, i.e. by using the partial event trees developed with only generic basic events, it is possible to organize a statistical data set applicable to every tunnel. The specific basic events - describing the traffic characteristics in the specific tunnel - are then implemented to complete the analysis.

3.3 Assessment of the Consequences

In a probabilistic risk analysis the risk is in general defined as:

$$R = \sum_{i=1}^n p_i C_i \quad (1)$$

where p_i is the probability of the scenario with associated consequences C_i and n the total number of scenarios to be considered. The statistical distribution of the consequences is in general accounted for by considering different gravity classes.

The consequences in the operability analysis are described by the expected shut down time of the line (both tracks) or of one track. In the societal risk analysis the consequences are represented by the expected number of victims. Thereby risk aversion is also considered by penalizing accidents with a large number of human losses. For that purpose three levels of consequences have been distinguished:

level 1: 0 - 20 losses
level 2: 21 - 200 losses
level 3: > 200 losses

The corresponding aversion factors were selected as 1, 3 and 10 (Basler and Partner, 1983). Such factors take into account the effective risk on the society i.e. they include the psychological effects of severe accidents.

4. DISCUSSION OF THE RESULTS

The main results of the operability analysis are presented in Table 2. The expected annual time of shut down are 1.5 and 11.8 hours for the line and a single track respectively. These values can be in general considered as acceptable compared to the unavailability of other transportation systems.

The societal risk analysis has been performed by assuming an average number of victims for each specified gravity class and by considering also the number of trains involved in each accidental scenario. The results are given in Table 3. The global risk level R_o has been computed as approximately 0.04 dead passengers per year resulting to a return period of 25 years. The major contribution results from the collision event, as demonstrated in Figure 2.. The global risk level including risk aversion R_e has been obtained as approximately 0.2 dead passengers per year indicating that the actual risk felt by the society is five times larger.

It is noted here that the obtained results are subject to uncertainties mainly due to:

- o statistical uncertainties of the implemented data;
- o uncertainties due to the fact that the risk assessment concerns a future operational period based however on past experience;
- o uncertainties related to the values of the branch probabilities in the event trees;
- o uncertainties associated to the quantification of the consequences.

A preliminary evaluation of the aforementioned uncertainties on appropriate statistical models showed that the obtained risk and operability values can be bounded by a lower and an upper limit which are 1.5 times less and 1.5 times higher than the obtained values respectively.

5. EVALUATION OF SAFETY MEASURES

Safety measures can be generally classified into the following categories:

- a) prevention measures;
- b) control and detection devices;
- c) mitigation measures.

The following prevention measures have been taken into account:

- o profile gauge;
- o loading gauge;
- o detector of irregularities on the surface of the wheels;
- o detector of hot boxes;
- o detector of locked brakes;
- o fire and smoke detector;
- o closed circuit television system.

Mitigation measures can include self-help activities (such as illumination) and rescue operations (such as rescue vehicles).

The effectiveness of each of the aforementioned safety measure has been evaluated on the basis of expert opinion and engineering judgement. The implementation of the prevention, control and detection measures result to a risk reduction of the order of 10% while the use of the mitigation measures reduce risk by 15%. Figure 3 illustrates the risk reduction due to the proposed safety measures.

It is therefore concluded that safety measures are important for the subject tunnel and the selection of the most effective measures can be performed on the basis of cost benefit considerations. In such a case safety and emergency illumination and prevention systems have been found to be the most efficient measures.

6. CONCLUSIONS

The risk analysis of a new 13 kilometers long twin track tunnel in the Northern Italy has been described in this contribution. Two different criteria have been thereby considered: the availability and the societal risk of the line.

Although there are no quantitative risk acceptance criteria in current railway standards the obtained values have been considered as appreciable since expected shut down times are low and return periods associated to accidents with human losses are considerable high especially if the proposed safety measures are implemented.

For future developments of the railway standards in view also of the long tunnels of the planned HSR European net a classification of the tunnels according to their length is proposed; for example small medium and great lengths can be distinguished. For each class a package of necessary safety measures shall be then recommended on the basis of results of risk quantitative analyses such as those illustrated herein.

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TABLE 1: OCCURRENCE RATES FOR THE SELECTED INITIATING EVENTS
(events per year)

INITIATING EVENT	ANNUAL OCCURRENCE RATE
Derailment	0.14
Collision	0.007
Crash against obstacles	0.06
Fire	0.05
Stop of the train	9.36

TABLE 2: RESULTS OF THE OPERABILITY ANALYSIS
(expected shut down in hours per year)

TYPE OF UNAVAILABILITY	DERAILMENT	COLLISION	CRASH AGAINST OBSTACLES	FIRE	TRAIN STOP	TOTAL
Line	0.36	0.26	0.10	0.31	0.42	1.45
Track	1.04	0.68	0.31	0.36	9.36	11.75

TABLE 3: RESULTS OF THE SOCIETAL RISK ANALYSIS

SOCIETAL RISK	DERAILMENT	COLLISION	CRASH AGAINST OBSTACLES	FIRE	TOTAL
R_o	9.6×10^{-3}	1.35×10^{-2}	5.7×10^{-3}	9.6×10^{-3}	3.84×10^{-2}
R_e	2.93×10^{-2}	1.12×10^{-2}	1.67×10^{-2}	4.96×10^{-2}	20.77×10^{-2}

Note:

R_o : societal risk in human losses per year;

R_e : societal risk including risk aversion in human losses per year.

Figure 1: Block diagram describing possible scenarios given the initiating event derailment (applicable to societal risk analysis)

LEGEND

- 1 DERAILMENT
- 2 COLLISION
- 3 CRASH AGAINST OBSTACLES
- 4 FIRE

Figure 2: Contribution to societal risk from the principal initiating events

LEGEND

- A PROFILE GAUGE
- B LOADING GAUGE
- C DETECTOR OF IRREGULARITIES ON THE SURFACE OF THE WHEELS
- D DETECTOR OF HOT BOXES
- E DETECTOR OF LOCKED BRAKES
- F FIRE AND SMOKE DETECTOR
- G CLOSED CIRCUIT TELEVISION SYSTEM
- H SAFETY AND EMERGENCY ILLUMINATION

Figure 3: Societal risk reduction associated to the proposed safety measures

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